

FOLK METHOD OF CURING VITAMIN DEFICIENCY IN POULTRY

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<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejmns-v03-i02-p1-27>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 04th February 2023

Accepted: 14th February 2023

Online: 15th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Vitamin deficiency, spinach,
turnip tops, grape leaves,
cilantro, dandelion leaves,
encephalomalacia, white
muscle disease, exudative
diathesis.

ABSTRACT

The article presents the data of scientific research on the treatment of vitamin deficiency D in poultry. The signs of vitamin deficiency, treatment with herbs and the addition of lower plants to food, the use of the biotechnology method were determined.

Introduction.

The benefit and ease of caring for an ordinary laying hen increases the livestock contained in numerous households every day. Not fastidiousness of chickens to the conditions of keeping and feeding, a long-proven and well-known fact. But it is the mass character and unpretentiousness of the bird that allows some farms and private poultry houses to violate all conceivable rules of feeding and maintenance. Causing not only the death of their own livestock, but also wider, mass outbreaks of epidemics. And, of course, the decisive factor directly affecting the quality of the laying hens is the long and cold winter. Along with the weather, the cause of poultry diseases is a lack of various vitamins. The disease begins to develop from a lack of vitamins and minerals in the diet of poultry, juicy feeds. The problem is mainly affected by poultry contained in cages, as well as not receiving balanced food in the winter season.

Methodology. To determine the various degrees of beriberi, scientific visual observations were conducted. Signs of vitamin deficiency were determined, such as weight loss and plumage; lethargy and weakness; disorder and improper bowel function; conjunctivitis; swelling of the joints; pale color of the crest and earrings. With neglected diseases, irreversible changes occur in the chicken's body and it can be quite difficult to completely cure it. In other cases, the introduction of balanced mixes, vitamin and mineral supplements, juicy feeds into the diet quickly helps poultry. In winter, laying hens need to be given hay, seashell and chalk.

In order for chickens to lay enough eggs, it is necessary to organize a proper diet, an important part of which are vitamins for egg production. If a bird is fed only with food, it will

not get the right amount of nutrients, so poultry farmers should know what kind of food and vitamin supplements pets need and when.

Results and discussion. Vitamin E deficiency is a metabolic disease that occurs with a lack of vitamin E, manifests itself in three forms: encephalomalacia, white muscle disease, exudative diathesis. Vitamin deficiency E- can be of exogenous and endogenous origin. Endogenous vitamin deficiency E occurs with a lack of selenium and sulfur-containing amino acids (methionine, cystine, etc.).

With a lack of the above listed, all kinds of birds get sick. It develops more often in chickens of meat breeds, the first manifestations at the age of 3-5 weeks.

Symptoms of vitamin E vitamin deficiency. With encephalomalacia, chickens have depression, shaky gait, ataxia, weakness of the legs, fall on their side, make swimming movements with their legs, tremor, torticollis, convulsions.

With white muscle disease - depression, decreased appetite, shaky gait, lameness, ruffled plumage, diarrhea, conjunctivitis.

With exudative diathesis - diffuse subcutaneous edema on the trunk and limbs of a greenish-blue color, covered with scabs, depression, lethargy, legs widely spaced.

With encephalomalacia - catarrhal enteritis; swelling of the brain (cerebellum), hemorrhages and greenish-yellow foci of softening in it, acquires a marble pattern. With white muscle disease - waxy necrosis of skeletal and cardiac muscles, thoracic and femoral muscles are dry, dull, flabby, gray-white or gray-yellow, with hemorrhages.

With exudative diathesis - serous edema of subcutaneous tissue with accumulation of light yellow or reddish fluid in it, the presence of scabs and crusts on the skin, loosening and swelling of skeletal muscles, ascites, hydropericarditis. The treatment is carried out in a comprehensive manner, taking into account the evaluation of feed. The provision of poultry with vitamin E, selenium, amino acids is taken into account. Differentiate from vitamin A hypovitaminosis, vitamin D hypovitaminosis, vitamin B hypovitaminosis, Newcastle disease, Marek. Compound feed is normalized according to the content of vitamin E. Additionally, preparations containing vitamin E and sodium selenite are soldered with water.

To achieve economically affordable and more effective results, we used folk remedies. For a long time our people have been using folk remedies, gifts of nature for the treatment of various diseases. Our nature is very rich in medicinal plants.

For the treatment of avitaminosis D in poultry, we used the following folk method. In summer, dandelion leaves, turnip tops, and grape leaves were dried in the shade. Since cilantro, cabbage and spinach in our country can be found in winter, we did not dry them.

The above plants in the composition contain vitamin E, even in raw or even dried, it is necessary to add crushed plants to food once a day. Dandelion leaves contain: fats - 0.70 g, proteins - 2.70 g, carbohydrates - 9.20 g, water - 85.60 g, ash - 1.80 g; turnip tops contain: fats - 0.30 g, proteins - 1.50 g, carbohydrates - 7.13 g, water - 89.67 g, ash - 1.40 g; cilantro (coriander leaves) contains: fats - 0.52 g, proteins — 2.13 g, carbohydrates - 3.67 g, water - 92.21 g, ash - 1.47 g; spinach contains: fats - 0.39 g, proteins - 2.86 g, carbohydrates - 3.63 g, water - 91.40 g, ash - 1.72 g; cabbage leaf contains: fats - 0.61 g, proteins - 3.02 g, carbohydrates - 5.42 g, water - 89.62 g, ash - 1.32 g; grape leaves contain: fats - 2.12 g, proteins - 5.60 g, carbohydrates - 17.31 g, water - 73.32 g, ash — 1.65 g.

In the morning, 300 grams to 500 grams of dried and 200 grams of fresh greens were added to the poultry feed with a weight of 5 kg. To improve food intake, kefir was given once a day with the addition of garlic and bitter pepper, which in turn increased the appetite and immunity of birds, improved metabolism in winter. Also, to achieve a better effect, 100 ml of the unicellular algae *Chlorella*- *Chlorella*, belonging to the department of Chlorophyta, was added to water and food every day.

Conclusions. As you can see from the above information, these plants are not only rich in vitamin E, but also rich in organic substances along with a group of other vitamins necessary to increase the viability of the poultry body. Economic damage includes losses from the death of poultry, reduced productivity, reduced hatchability of chickens and the cost of prevention and elimination of the disease. According to individual authors (Dorn, 1966, Willemart and Schneider, 1964), the mortality rate of chickens is 20-25%, but can reach 60-90% (Samberg, 1964, Schneider, 1964). But in our experiments, the mortality rate reached 30-40%, since we added spinach, cilantro and turnip tops in fresh form to the poultry diet every day.

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